

Community perceptions of climate-change vulnerability in Seychelles and some considerations on data and methodological gaps

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1. Introduction

Climate change is one of the greatest challenges facing the world's environment, society and economy today. Its expected repercussions, which include worsening droughts and crop failures, rising sea level, more frequent and intense storms, and extinction of species, will impact every nation on earth (Handmer et al., 2012). Climate change impacts can already be seen across the globe and Seychelles will not be immune. Recognizing that climate change is a threat to national development, hence the need to plan adaptation and mitigation measures concomitantly that minimize current and potential vulnerabilities (Dumenu and Obeng, 2016). As a result, some studies have been conducted to assess climate-change impacts, vulnerability, and adaptation strategies in Small Island Developing States - SIDS (Betzold, 2015; Mercer et al., 2012), Sub Saharan Africa – SSA (Twomlow et al., 2008), and other developing countries (Sovacool et al., 2012).

Vulnerability is a multidimensional process affected by social, political, and economic forces interacting across different levels ranging from local and/or community, districts, national, regional to international. In this paper, vulnerability is defined 'as a function of exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity' (Engle, 2011). Recognizing that many factors influence vulnerability, Thomas et al. (2018) identified four broad themes as particularly helpful for understanding the social aspects of vulnerability such as resource access, governance, culture, and knowledge. Therefore, any effort to reduce vulnerability requires an understanding of why it exists in the first place, corroborated by established approaches that examine issues of power and social differences. Conceptualizing vulnerability is a central element within climate-change discourse owing to the significance of questions such as: who and what is vulnerable to certain climatic stressors, where may these be located, how may various societal or natural conditions amplify this vulnerability, and what can be done to respond to, and reduce these vulnerabilities? (Gabrielsson et al., 2013).

Social and ecological systems are sufficiently complex that our knowledge of them, and our ability to predict their future dynamics, will never be complete (Berkes, 2007). Vulnerability as a concept lies in its inclusive nature in socio-ecological systems within the framework of

resilience thinking, whereby humans and the natural environment are seen as intimately coupled and differentially exposed, differentially sensitive, and differentially adaptable to threats (Polsky et al. 2007). Studying this is difficult, because it demands a thorough investigation of every biophysical, social, cultural and cognitive aspect of human–environment interactions. These theoretical developments have lured scientists into the trap of simplifying the complexity and uncertainty of a specific vulnerability system to such an extent that it may no longer be helpful for our overall understanding of what vulnerability entails (Ingram et al., 2010; Patt et al., 2009). This doesn't imply that vulnerability assessment shouldn't be contextualized, rather it should adapt methodologies to reflect local realities given that adaptation actions are likely to be site specific in most cases.

More importantly, SIDS share a common vulnerability to climate change with similar impacts such as ocean warming, sea-level rise, changing precipitation patterns, and increased intensity of tropical storms (Klöck and Nunn, 2019). Given these challenges faced by SIDS, adaptation is considered a national priority in Seychelles in order to reduce its vulnerability to the impacts of climate change. Despite such importance of adaptation, a comprehensive study on vulnerability assessment in Seychelles is lacking. In such a situation, the adaptation landscape is likely to be dominated by reactive adaptation action with little consideration for planned or anticipatory adaptation action. Moreover, planned adaptation actions might also lead to maladaptation if such strategies are not guided by scientific evidence. The impact of climate change on coastal livelihoods as a result of sea-level rise, storm and tidal surges, extreme sea-surface temperatures, and coastal flooding will have serious consequences on livelihoods, the economy and human security in Seychelles. This study draws on some lessons from the Ecosystem Based Adaptation (EbA) project in Seychelles while highlighting some data and methodological gaps (such as major and sub-major components relevant to the Seychelles context that were not included) within the framework of community perceptions on vulnerability. Guidelines on framing vulnerability indicators, based on standard methodologies, are provided alongside recommendations for future vulnerability studies in Seychelles. Such studies are needed in Seychelles where imminent vulnerabilities are present (Etongo, 2019) and where such integrative investigations are missing.

2. Vulnerability to climate change – definition and framing

There are different definitions of vulnerability to climate change whilst there is little consensus about its precise meaning (Fellmann, 2012). Despite the various definitions of vulnerability, the most comprehensive and widely used is that provided by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2000): ‘... the degree to which a system is susceptible to, or unable to cope with adverse effects of climate change, including climate variability and extremes.

Vulnerability is a function of the character, magnitude, rate of climate variation to which a system is exposed, its sensitivity, and its adaptive capacity.’ Thus vulnerability of any system is frequently considered as a function of three elements: exposure to a hazard, sensitivity to that hazard, and the capacity of the system to cope with and adapt to or recover from the effects of those conditions which are mostly referred to as adaptive capacity (Reed et al., 2013).

Exposure is the level and extent to which a system is exposed to major climate change (Tao et al., 2011); and sensitivity is the degree to which a system is affected, either adversely or beneficially, by climate-related stimuli. The effect may be direct (e.g., a change in crop yield in response to a change in the mean, range, or variability of temperature) or indirect (e.g., damages caused by an increase in the frequency of coastal flooding due to sea level rise) (IPCC, 2000). Additionally, adaptive capacity is the ability or potential of a system to respond successfully to climate variability and change and includes adjustments in behaviour, resources and technologies. The most widely used approach to the assessment of climate change vulnerability is based on the definition proposed by the IPCC. In this regard Smit and Wandel (2006) corroborated that the literature consistently considers vulnerability as a function of three elements – exposure, sensitivity, and the adaptive capacity as outlined schematically in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Key components of vulnerability, illustrating the relationship between exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity (Source: IPCC, 2007a)

However, there are many ways and techniques to assess the vulnerability to climate change often aimed at informing the development of policies that reduce the risks associated with climate change (Reed et al., 2013). Vulnerability assessments may look at either social vulnerability or environmental vulnerability or consider the interplay of both; and therefore each study should consider the scope, purpose, scale, and the audience for their research (Byrne, 2014). Pearson et al. (2011) believe that, because of the different conceptualizations of vulnerability, there are different ways of assessing it and it is quite common for these sometimes to overlap with each other. The indicator approach is a method that could be used to measure vulnerability (Mbakahya and Ndiema, 2015). This method is based on developing a range of indicators and selecting some of them through expert judgment, principal component analysis, or correlation with past disaster events. So in this method, indicators and selection procedures are crucial to the assessment of vulnerability. Although there are different indicators for evaluating climate change vulnerability, as Fellmann (2012) argued, the significance of particular indicators can vary in different regions since vulnerability is place based and context specific.

3. Study area, materials and methods

3.1. Study area

This study was conducted within the framework of the Ecosystem-Based Adaptation through South-South Cooperation in Seychelles. Community and household vulnerability to climate change across eight districts on Mahé Island (see Fig. 2) was the focus of this study. Despite similarity in the Human Development Index across Mahé Island, community vulnerability to the impacts of climate change are likely to differ in relation to sensitivity, exposure and adaptive capacity. Such disparities are expected due to differences in socio-economic, ecosystems, and even environmental conditions linked to location factors. Through stakeholder consultations, the criteria on which the case study districts were selected are as follows: mangrove sites having invasive alien species that needed to be eradicated and replanted; national highways to be protected from coastal erosion through embankment stabilization using mangrove restoration; and areas that needed the construction of culverts or replacement in order to improve the hydrological flow through artificially fragmented mangroves/wetlands.

Port Launay, for example, is located in the Port Glaud District in the north western part of Mahé. The livelihood activities across the district include artisanal fishing, agriculture, small-scale industrial processing, hospitality and service industry. The Roche Caiman district on the other hand was created mostly from reclaimed land with the dominant livelihood activity being tourism and artisanal fishing. Anse Boileau is situated on the west coast of Mahé but

the district itself has a mountainous topography and the main road is by the coast. This district is quite large with a population of about 4,176 inhabitants scattered in its almost seventeen sub-districts from hill tops and along the coast of the district. The district of Cascade is located along the East Coast of Mahé (Fig. 2.) which stands apart as it has its own distinct culture. The district was named after the small tributaries that ‘cascade’ into a big river to the sea. Therefore, differences in the nature of the topography, livelihood and land-use activities are likely to influence community vulnerability across these communities and over time (GoS, 2013).

Figure 2. Map of Mahé Island highlighting the eight case study communities

Climate change projections suggest that the latest temperature trends based on maximum and minimum temperature show warming between $+0.33^{\circ}$ and $+0.82^{\circ}$ respectively and are significantly warmer than previously assessed in the Initial National Communication (GoS,

2009). Furthermore, annual sea-level rise has increased at an average rate of +1.8mm per annum over the 1961 to 2003 period, which is consistent with the global average (Chang-Seng, 2007). There is a potential for an increased frequency and intensity of tropical storms (and their associated tidal surges) and such changes will all contribute towards increased risks for low-lying coastal areas in Seychelles. The fact that the warmest months receive the least rainfall is an important limiting factor for agricultural production (Etongo, 2019). Climatic hazards, such as flooding and drought, are recurring phenomena in Seychelles and are being reported more and more frequently. These climatic hazards affect livelihoods and the economy, especially the most climate-sensitive economic sectors such as water resources, agriculture, coastal infrastructures, and forest ecosystems.

3.2. Selection of vulnerability indicators in the current study

A household vulnerability index was developed to indicate the extent to which households at the potential sites are susceptible to sustaining damage from climate change. Based on an extensive literature review of assessments on climate change vulnerability, environmental and socio-economic indicators were identified to reflect the vulnerability components. The selected indicators represent both the biophysical and the socioeconomic conditions of selected local communities on Mahé Island. The methodology and indicators used to estimate the components of the vulnerability index are detailed further in Figure 3 and Appendix I.

Figure 3. Indicators of climate-change vulnerability and their inter-linkages with some examples, as applied in the current study

3.3. Sampling and data collection

Household surveys were conducted across several communities (see Table 1) in order to capture the community's perception on climate change vulnerability in Seychelles. The household data gathered included socio-demographic profile of households, livelihood activities including income from natural resources, climate change awareness, local perceptions on climate variability on climate sensitive natural resources and the environment. In order to assess how climate change and vulnerability are changing over time, there is a need to periodically repeat this household survey at each site. This explains why the survey that started in 2014 was repeated in 2016, 2017 and 2018 (see Table 1). Around each site, communities that were supposed to benefit directly from the project intervention e.g. tree planting and training activities, were identified. After the identification of a beneficiary community, a total of 15 households were randomly selected for the survey and the same sets of questions were applied across all the case study communities.

Table 1: Household surveys conducted by the EBA project in Seychelles

Year	Surveyed Districts	Household Surveys
2014	Cascade, Cossovo, Port Launay, Roche Caiman	34
2016	Port Launay, Anse Gouvernement, Anse Royale, Roche Caiman, Curieuse	63
2017	Anse Aux Pins, Anse Boileau, Anse La Mouche, Anse Royale, Bel Ombre, Cascade, Port Launay	93
2018	Anse Aux Pins, Anse Boileau, Anse La Mouche, Anse Royale, Bel Ombre, Cascade, Port Launay, Roche Caiman	103

A total of 293 household surveys were completed between the year 2014 and 2018. Surveys in some of these districts were repeated (e.g. Anse Royale and Port Launay) between 2016 and 2018 not necessarily with the same households. This paper draws on some of the more general pattern shown by households during the different years as indicated in Table 1, while

examining the indicators applied in this study in order to address data and methodological gaps as a way of improving future studies on vulnerabilities.

3.4. Calculation of the vulnerability index

The vulnerability index was calculated through the following equations:

- ◆ The exposure index was expressed as the sum of the scores for indicators 1 – 7 (see Appendix II for questions 1 – 23).

$$Exposure = \left(\sum_i^{iv} score_indicator \right)$$

- ◆ The sensitivity index was expressed as the sum of the scores for indicators 8 – 19.

$$Sensitivity = \left(\sum_v^x score_indicator \right)$$

- ◆ The adaptive capacity index was expressed as the sum of the scores for indicators 20 – 23.

$$Adaptive\ capacity = \left(\sum_{xi}^{xiv} score_indicator \right)$$

- ◆ The vulnerability index was expressed as the product of sensitivity and exposure minus adaptive capacity.

$$Vulnerability = (Exposure \times Sensitivity) - Adaptive\ capacity$$

A score system of 0, 1, and 2 was used to assign different weighting on indicators to assess household vulnerability. Drought for example as a component of exposure was assessed among households based on the score system as follows: 0 – has not experienced drought events in the recent past, 1 – has experienced frequent droughts episodes in recent past with no negative effects on household, and 2 – has experienced frequent droughts episodes in recent past with negative effects on household. This method was applied for other indicators and for more detail see Appendix I. The collected data were analysed using Microsoft Excel Version 2013 and the results presented as figures.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Livelihood activities across the selected communities

Fishing was the main livelihood activity for 31% of the households followed by ‘other’ activities (Fig. 4). It doesn’t come as a surprise that the majority of community members were engaged in fishing because Seychelles is highly dependent on its Blue Economy. The category ‘other’ were households involved in small-scale businesses, sale of labour, transportation, etc. Globally, fisheries support the livelihoods of over half a billion people who are exposed to multiple climatic stresses and shocks that affect their capacity to subsist – a view supported by Islam et al. (2014).

Figure 4. Livelihood activities that support community members across the case study sites

Many of the people dependent on small-scale fisheries live in developing countries and face climatic shocks and stresses such as cyclones, floods, droughts, sea-level rise, land erosion, and temperature and rainfall fluctuations (IPCC, 2007b). Furthermore, a livelihood encompasses people’s capabilities, assets, income and activities required to secure the

necessities of life. It's considered sustainable when it enables people to cope with, and recover from, shocks and stresses (such as natural disasters and economic or social upheavals) and enhance their wellbeing and that of future generations without undermining the natural environment or resource base. Therefore, agricultural activities and fishing are climate-sensitive livelihoods in Seychelles that are vulnerable to the impacts of climate change such as drought, flooding, ocean warming and ocean acidification.

4.2. Exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity between years compared

The exposure of the selected communities to the impacts of climate change showed slight increases in the years 2016 and 2018 with the highest exposure recorded by the former (see Fig. 5). Given that households/districts surveyed each year were different (see Table 1), a temporal investigation could have yielded much better results if the households and districts were the same. On the other hand, the sensitivity of livelihood activities across the case study communities shows a slight decrease from 2014 to 2018. Seychelles has a land area of 445km² and just like other SIDS it suffers from the most common environmental problems such as land degradation, coastal erosion, flooding, loss of biodiversity, etc. due to its smallness, remoteness from the mainland and world markets, and high exposure to natural disasters (Scandurra et al., 2018; Khan and Amelie, 2014). Surprisingly, the adaptive capacity dropped significant in the year 2016 when compared to 2014 and stays fairly the same in the years 2016, 2017 and 2018 (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Comparison of exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity across different years in the case study communities

Adaptive Capacity (AC) also refers to capabilities, resources and institutions for implementing effective adaptation measures. Additionally, AC plays an important role in designing effective adaptation strategies in which the ultimate aim is to reduce vulnerability to climate change. Measuring adaptive capacity as a key component of vulnerability assessments has become one of the most challenging topics in the climate-change adaptation context (Marzi et al., 2018). Although Ecosystem-Based Adaptation to Climate Change projects, either completed or ongoing, have been implemented in some communities in Seychelles, especially on Mahé Island, it should be reiterated that reducing the vulnerability of livelihoods, ecosystems and the environment to the impacts of climate change is a continuous process and not a project outcome. This is because the extent, intensity and distribution of the impacts of climate change constitute uncertainties that have repositioned humanity to engage in adaptation actions as a learning-doing-process. Furthermore, adaptation is relatively new, especially among some government ministries in Seychelles, and the need for human and institutional capacity building is invaluable in achieving lower levels of vulnerabilities – a view supported by Etongo (2019).

4.3. Exposure, sensitivity, and adaptive capacity in case study communities

In terms of exposure to the impacts of climate change, Anse La Mouche, Cascade and Anse Royale recorded the highest values, while the lowest was recorded by Anse Boileau (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. Vulnerability assessment of the case study communities based on 2018 data

Seychelles being a small island nation surrounded by the Indian Ocean remains vulnerable to the effects of climate change. One clearly visible sign of such vulnerability lies on the archipelago's coastline where several shorelines have been subjected to intense degradation and erosion. Anse La Mouche (Bay of the Fly) in the western part of Mahé, and even the shoreline near the jetty on third most populated island of La Digue, are examples of regions that have witnessed coastal erosion (see Fig. 7) mainly due to rising sea level as well as stronger waves which remove large portions of sand from the beaches.

Figure 7. The eroded beach and exposed tree roots at Anse La Mouche back in 2011.
(Photo Credit: Seychelles News Agency)

The highest three values on sensitivity to climate change were recorded in Cascade, Anse Aux Pins and Anse Royale (Fig. 6). Some of the climate-sensitive sectors in Seychelles include agriculture, fisheries, tourism, water resources, forest, etc. Reference is made to the severe flooding and landslides in Seychelles, particularly in three districts on the southeast coast of Mahé (Au Cap, Pointe Larue, and Cascade) that occurred in 2013. According to the GoS (2013), the rainfall which represented 66% of the long-term average overwhelmed existing natural and constructed drainage systems and retaining walls, causing floods and landslides, resulting in damage to homes and other critical infrastructures. Aside from the sensitivity, Anse Aux Pins had the highest adaptive capacity index followed by Anse La Mouche and

Anse Royale. Greater adaptive capacity contributes to reducing vulnerability to future climate change and increasing resilience. Marzi et al. (2018) are of the view that, AC is associated with a range of socioeconomic, governance and development – such as economic resources, knowledge and technology – infrastructures and institutional quality. This is true also in the case of Seychelles given that the socioeconomic and biophysical landscape is not homogenous but rather heterogeneous, with disparity among communities in terms of available financial and human resources in order to improve their adaptive capacities to the impacts of climate change.

4.4. Vulnerability and climate-change awareness

Despite some differences in vulnerability in the year 2014, when compared to 2016, 2017 and 2018, the overall pattern seems relatively low (Fig. 8). However, such a result based on annual aggregate often masks vulnerabilities that might be specific to different income groups, livelihood activities and sectors. For example, several households are dependent on climate-sensitive livelihood activities such as agriculture, fisheries, tourism and forest resources and unmasking such vulnerabilities will pave the way for targeted policies that can reduce the vulnerability of Seychelles through the implementation of proactive adaptation measures while concomitantly reducing the risk of maladaptation.

Figure 8. Climate change awareness and vulnerability across different time-scale across the case-study communities

Climate-change awareness was relatively high for all the years during which data was gathered for the EbA South-South project in Seychelles (Fig. 8). Community members have received sensitization on climate change from different channels especially through two NGOs – Sustainability for Seychelles (S4S) and Wildlife Clubs of Seychelles (WCS). Climate-change education, The Global Day of Action for Climate Change, climate match and different forms of climate activism with school children and youth were instrumental between 2014 and 2018 in raising awareness among the population of Seychelles on the impacts of climate change.

Local television stations, radio programs and newspapers have also carried headlines on issues such as coastal erosion, flooding and coral bleaching via the three official languages in Seychelles as a way to sensitize the population. In fact, the coral-bleaching event of 2016, just like the one that occurred in 1997, affected the second most important economic activity in the country – the fishing sector. Given that the coral bleaching event is a repeat of the 1997 event, and was widely reported through different communication channels, corroborates the results of a relatively higher level of climate-change awareness in Seychelles. More importantly, adaptation to climate change is considered a national priority and that has provided a platform on issues related to climate change to be discussed at different levels, and even to be integrated into school programs and curriculums.

5. Data and methodological gap

The data gathered through the EbA South-South project in Seychelles, in order to address the topic on community perceptions of climate-change vulnerability, is weakened by data gaps emanating from lacunae in the methodology used. For example, the indicator approach which is instrumental and widely used to measure vulnerability (Mbakahya and Ndiema, 2015) was applied during the data collection. Despite an attempt to collect data on socio-economics, environmental conditions, natural resources, and climate-change awareness, huge gaps do occur in the data which, in turn, mask some specificity in terms of vulnerability among households and communities in Seychelles. The livelihood Vulnerability Index (LVI) if properly contextualized could have benefited the current study by adapting standard methodologies applied in other case studies. A good example could have been the study of Hahn et al. (2009) that uses both major and sub-components in developing a LVI for two communities in Mozambique. Additionally, the major household components applied in the study included the following: (i) socio-demographic profile, (ii) livelihood activities, (iii) health, (iv) social networks, (v) food, (vi) water, and (vii) natural disasters and climate variability.

In the Seychelles case study, issues related to health and social networks were not included while those that were included lacked relevant information. A distinction on the major components and their corresponding sub-components could have gone a long way in generating household specific vulnerability indexes rather than general results across communities and over different time-scales, as was the case with the current data in this study. Climate-change vulnerability across different sectors could have been another important context for the EbA South-South project. The study of Dunford et al. (2015), in which climate-change vulnerability across sectors was assessed, is another methodology that could have been adopted in the current study. Although there are different indicators for evaluating climate-change vulnerability, as Fellmann (2012) argued, the significance of particular indicators can vary in different regions since vulnerability is place based and context specific. However, such indicators should be modified to suit local realities; but must be guided by existing frameworks to ensure that results can be comparable or can be scaled up to sites with similar circumstances. This was the case with two studies conducted in Ghana in which methodologies on vulnerability were contextualized with indicators that reflect local realities.

One of the studies in the Ghanaian example characterized the nature of household vulnerability to climate variability (Antwi-Agyei et al., 2013). In this case study, the major components for the LVI included the following: social capital, human capital, natural capital, financial capital, physical capital and livelihood diversification. These are important categorizations that were not captured fully in the current study (see Appendix I). The implication in the Seychelles case study is that the dynamics of household and community vulnerability across these major components is masked. The second study took a narrow perspective to address social vulnerability based on three major components – demographic, economic and social alongside their corresponding indicators (Dumenu and Obeng, 2016). Such contextualization is important when attempting to disentangle vulnerabilities to climate change that are socially oriented. Despite the contextualization, the selection of indicators was based on expert judgment – one of three methods used in selecting indicators for a vulnerability assessment with the others being principal component analysis, and/or correlation with past disaster events (Cutter et al., 2003; Brooks et al., 2005). Although values ranging from 0-2 were used during the data collection for the current study, it remains unclear how the weightings for each value were derived.

6. Conclusion and way forward

Major livelihood activities in Seychelles, such as fishing and agriculture, are climate sensitive and exposed to the impacts of climate variability and change. Aside from fishing and

agriculture, the tourism industry which contributes the highest GDP to the Seychelles economy is also vulnerable to the impacts of climate change as this sector is highly dependent on the environment and natural resources. A healthy marine ecosystem is important for scuba divers. However, coral reefs are vulnerable to the impacts of climate change such as ocean warming thereby leading to coral bleaching. The coral bleaching events in 1997 and 2016 in Seychelles contributed to the death of corals which in turn affected the fishery sector.

The results obtained from the study provided an overview on vulnerability over different years and case study communities during the project cycle. In terms of exposure to the impacts of climate change, Anse La Mouche, Cascade and Anse Royale recorded the highest index while for sensitivity it was Cascade, Anse Aux Pins, and Anse Royale. That notwithstanding, the dynamics of vulnerability among households was especially important for communities such as Cascade and Anse Royale that are both exposed and sensitive to the impacts of climate change.

Given that studies that address vulnerability assessment in Seychelles are still in their infancy, despite adaption is now a national priority, some recommendations are provided as a way forward to generate science that could influence policies and adaptation actions. Some of the areas for future research include firstly, a quantitative assessment of vulnerability to climate change across the 28 districts in Seychelles. Such a study should be carefully designed taking into account the three components of vulnerability to develop indicators for exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity. The data gathered through these indicators should be analysed using a Geographic Information System (GIS) to generate maps of vulnerability index across districts – high, medium and low vulnerability. Secondly, exploring climate-change vulnerability across sectors in Seychelles is invaluable and needed urgently. Thirdly, given the importance of the fishery sector within the framework of the Blue Economy in Seychelles, a study that addresses the vulnerability of fishery-based livelihoods to the impacts of climate variability and change in Seychelles is no longer an option but imperative.

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Dr Daniel Etongo obtained his PhD in Forest Ecology from the Viikki Tropical Resources Institute (VITRI), Helsinki University, Finland. His research focuses on biodiversity assessment, socio-ecological system modelling, climate change adaptation and mitigation. Following his PhD, Dr Etongo was recruited as a postdoc at VITRI, Helsinki University in the Biocarbon and Rural Development (BIODEV) project implemented across four West African countries. During this period, he acted as International Climate Change Expert in which two high-profile workshops were organized in Freetown, Sierra Leone in collaboration with the World Agroforestry Centre (ICRAF) and Sierra Leone Agricultural Research Institute (SLARI) on the Post Paris Climate Deal. Before joining the University of Seychelles (UniSey), Daniel worked as a postdoc at Maynooth University, Ireland for an EU H2020 project implemented in Ethiopia, Malawi, Uganda and South Africa. Daniel joined the University of Seychelles in 2018 as a Senior Lecturer in the Department of Environment and is a research member of the James Michel Blue Economy Research Institute (BERI). He teaches courses, at graduate and undergraduate level, including Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation, Ecosystem-Based Management, and Ecosystem-Based Disaster Risk Reduction. He also represents UniSey on the Seychelles National Climate Change Committee.

Terence Vel worked as a science laboratory technician for approximately 16 years in various secondary schools in Seychelles before joining the University of Seychelles (Unisey) in 2015 as a science laboratory technician for the Environmental Science Programmes. Twenty-five years ago he became a co-founder of Wildlife Clubs of Seychelles and during this time has managed the organization's projects

and coordinated environmental programmes in 40 schools on Mahé, Praslin and La Digue. In the year 2000, Terence worked as a technician on a project called 'Avian ecosystems in Seychelles', which was funded by the Global Environment Facility and implemented by the former Birdlife Seychelles. In this project, he co-authored a paper entitled 'Biodiversity Surveys and Conservation Potential of Inner Seychelles Islands' (Issue No 495, issued by: National Museum of Natural History Smithsonian Institution Washington, D.C. U.S.A July 2002.) In 2008 Terence embarked on studies for a diploma in environmental education and social marketing at the University of Kent's School of Anthropology and Conservation. This led him to The Darwin Initiative Rare Pride Campaign to work on a project called 'investing in island biodiversity: restoring the Seychelles paradise flycatcher'. His fields of competence include Ecology, Communication/Media, Sustainable Development, Biodiversity Conservation, Environment Education and Community outreach/Social Marketing.

***Amanda Port-Louis** is currently working as a project assistant for the Wildlife Clubs of Seychelles (WCS) under a Mangrove Restoration Management project. Five years ago, she completed her studies in Biology, Chemistry and Mathematics at the School of Advanced Level Studies, at the same time she became a member of the WCS. In 2016, she gained admission to pursue an undergraduate degree in Environmental Sciences and she graduated in the year 2019 with a Bachelor's degree in Environmental Science at the University of Seychelles. Her third-year project was entitled 'Seychelles Magpie Robin: Population dynamics and food availability across different types of habitat on Fregate Island'. She has broadened her field experience on environmental issues through volunteerism with Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) such as Seychelles Island Foundation, Island Conservation Society, Fregate Island Private and The Ocean Project Seychelles. Amanda is now a member of The Ocean Project Seychelles where she participates in research relating to the marine litter monitoring project and also is part of a team that raises awareness about plastic pollution and its impacts on the environment and the Blue Economy of Seychelles.*

Appendix I

Indicators of vulnerability included in the household survey

Index	Component indicator	Unit of measurement	Score		
			0	1	2
Exposure	i) Changes in temperature	Household	No change	Has increased with no noticeable negative effects on household	Has increased with negative effects on household
	ii) Changes in rainfall patterns	Household	No change	Shift in seasons with no impact on household	Shift in seasons with negative impact on household
	iii) Changes in rainfall intensity	Household	No change	Increased/decreased impact of rainfall with no impact on household	Increased/decreased impact of rainfall with negative effects on household
	iv) Drought episodes	Household	Has not experienced drought events in the recent past	Has experienced frequent drought episodes in recent past with no negative effects on household	Has experienced frequent drought episodes in recent past with negative effects on household
	v) Flooding events	Household	Has not experienced flooding events in the recent past	Has experienced frequent flooding events in recent past with no negative effects on household	Has experienced frequent flooding events in recent past with negative effects on household
	vi) Storm surges	Household	Has not experienced storm surge events in the recent past	Has experienced frequent storm surges in recent past with no negative effects on household	Has experienced frequent storm surge events in recent past with negative effects on household
	vii) Coastal erosion	Household	Has not experienced coastal erosion in the recent past	Has experienced frequent coastal erosion in recent past with no negative effects on household	Has experienced frequent coastal erosion in recent past with negative effects on household

Index	Component indicator	Unit of measurement	Score		
			0	1	2
	viii) Saltwater intrusion	Household	Has not experienced saltwater intrusion into groundwater in the recent past	Has experienced frequent saltwater intrusion into groundwater in the recent past with no negative effects on household	Has experienced frequent saltwater intrusion into groundwater in the recent past with negative effects on household
Sensitivity	ix) Slope failures	Household/ local community	Household members reported no slope failures around their village	Household members reported slope failures around their village with no negative impact on local community	Household members reported slope failures around their village with negative impact on local community
	x) Soil fertility	Household	Household members report no change	Household members perceive soil fertility to have decreased with no negative impact on family	Household members perceive soil fertility to have decreased with negative impact on family
	xi) Fisheries productivity	Household/ local community	Household members report no change	Household members perceive fisheries productivity to have decreased with no negative impact on family	Household members perceive fisheries productivity to have decreased with negative impact on family
	xii) Changes in natural environment ¹	Household	Household members report no change	Experience change with no negative impact on household	Experience change with negative impact on household
	xiii) Dependency level ²	Household	Household size is less than three members	Household size ranging from four to nine members	Household size of over nine members
	xiv) Irrigation	Household	100% Irrigation	Part irrigation, part rain fed	100% rain fed
	xv) Livelihood sources	Household	Household members rely on multiple livelihood sources	Household members rely on more than one product for their livelihoods (e.g. agricultural diversification)	Household members rely on only one product (e.g. crop type and/or livestock product) for their livelihoods

Index	Component indicator	Unit of measurement	Score		
			0	1	2
Adaptive capacity	xvi) Awareness ³	Household	Household representative has awareness index of 0–30%	Household representative has awareness index of 30–60%	Household representative has awareness index of 60–100%
	xvii) Information	Household	Household representative never receives information on climate change and adaptation	Household representative receives information on climate change and adaptation intermittently	Household representative consistently receives information on climate change and adaptation
	xviii) Surplus production	Household	Household's total food production is used for own consumption (100% own consumption)	Less than 30% of household's total food production is sold	More than 30% of household's total food production is sold
	xix) Response: change in agricultural practices	Household	Household members have not perceived any changes in the climate and have not taken any remedial action	Household members have perceived climate variability and its related effects on production and income but have not changed their agricultural practices	Household members have perceived climate variability and its related effects on production and income and have therefore responded by adopting new agricultural practices (e.g. seed change)

¹ Changes in natural environment are related to Section 4 of the household-survey questionnaire (Appendix II). This indicator is estimated by households reporting changes in soil cover, levels of river sedimentation, water salinity, river ecosystems, forest size, and the presence of invasive species.

² Dependency level is measured by household size.

³ See the following section for details on the calculation of the awareness index.

Appendix II

Sample of household survey

Ecosystem-based Adaptation South Seychelles
Household survey to determine climate change awareness and vulnerability

Questionnaire number: _____ Date: _____

Village/Town: _____ GPS Location: _____

General

1. Name of Interviewer: _____

2. Name of Interviewee (*Head of Household*): _____

3. Gender (*circle*): M/F

4. Marital status (*circle*): (1) married (2) single (3) widowed (4) de facto

5. Number of dependants (*circle*): (1) less than 3 (2) 3 – 5 (3) 6 – 9 (4) 10 – 13
(5) more than 13

Livelihoods

6. Main livelihood source (*circle*): (1) Farming (2) Fishing (3) Non-timber Forest Products (NTFPs)
(4) Labour selling (5) Trade/sales (6) Crafts (7) Transport
(8) Tourism (9) Government (10) Other (please specify): _____

7. Please write down (in the first column) the sources of income and food that the Interviewee relies on. Mark with an “x” if they sell and / or consume. If they sell specific crops, fish or other commodities, please write the revenue received per month

Livelihood source e.g. Farm produce, livestock, fishing, crafts, wages	Consume (X)	Sell (X)	Revenue/month

8. On average, what percentage (%) of your total production (crops, livestock, fish) do you sell?
(write): _____

9. In the case of farmers, how do you water your crops? (circle):

- (1) rainwater only (2) irrigation all the time (3) irrigation only during the dry season

Income from Natural Resources

10. Please write down (in the first column) the Natural Resources from which the Interviewee receives livelihoods. Please include products such as firewood, fish, fruits, medicine and other relevant items. Mark with an "x" if they sell and/or consume. If they sell the commodity, please write the revenue received per month.

NTFPs	Consume/use (X)	Sell (X)	Revenue/month

Climate Change Awareness/Adaptation

11. Have you heard of Climate Change? If yes, can you tell me what it is?

(ask question and listen to answer – circle one of the following using your discretion)

- 1) Interviewee has never heard of it
- 2) Interviewee has heard of it, but has limited understanding
- 3) Interviewee understands what it is and feels the effects (does not mention causes)
- 4) Interviewee understands the causes and effects

12. What is currently causing Climate Change?

(ask question and listen to answer – circle one of the following using your discretion)

- 1) Natural causes
- 2) Humans
- 3) Natural causes and humans
- 4) Not sure

13. Have you felt the effects of climate change?

(ask question and listen to answer – circle one of the following using your discretion)

- 1) No/not sure
- 2) Maybe (gives examples relating to extreme hazards)
- 3) Yes (gives examples relating to long-term trends of climate change)
- 4) Yes (gives examples of long-term trends of climate change and describes how they affect livelihoods)

14. If you have felt the effects of climate change, has it affected your production or income from livestock/crop production/fisheries?

(circle) Y/N

15. If yes, have you changed your practices to cope with this effect?

(circle) Y/N

16. How have you changed these practices?

(write) _____

17. How often do you receive information (or training) to cope with climate change? (circle)

- 1) Never
- 2) Once (received information once)
- 3) Sometimes (receives information/training intermittently)
- 4) Often (receives information/training more than once a year)

18. How often do you talk about climate change? (circle)

- 1) Never
- 2) Rarely (once a month)
- 3) Sometimes (once a week)
- 4) Often (more than once a week)

Vulnerability

19. Ask the Interviewee if she/he has noticed changes associated with climate over the past 5 years and tick the correct box. If she/he has noticed a change, please also ask how this has affected her/his family. Write down these answers in notes section below.

Climatic variation				If increased/decreased/more frequent/less frequent, please describe effect on family		
Temperature	No change	Increased	Decreased	None	Positive	Negative
Droughts	No change	More frequent	Less frequent	None	Positive	Negative
Floods	No change	More frequent	Less frequent	None	Positive	Negative
Storm surges	No change	More frequent	Less frequent	None	Positive	Negative
Coastal erosion	No change	More frequent	Less frequent	None	Positive	Negative
Saltwater intrusion	No change	More frequent	Less frequent	None	Positive	Negative
Rainfall (timing)	No change	Wet season comes later in the year	Wet season comes earlier in the year	None	Positive	Negative
Rainfall (impact)	No change	Rainfall is heavier	Rainfall is lighter	None	Positive	Negative

Notes:

20. Ask the Interviewee if she/he has noticed changes associated with natural resources over the past 5 years and tick the correct box. If she/he has noticed a change, please also ask how this has affected her/his family. Write down these answers in the notes section below.

Environmental conditions/response to climatic variations				If increased/decreased, please describe effect on family			
Soil fertility	No change	Increased	Decreased	None	Positive	Negative	
Slope failures	No change	More frequent	Less frequent	None	Positive	Negative	
Fisheries productivity	No change	More frequent	Less frequent	None	Positive	Negative	
Changes in natural environment	Forests and natural vegetation	No change	Less forest coverage	More forest coverage	None	Positive	Negative
	Crop/livelihood pests	No change	More pests	Fewer pests	None	Positive	Negative
	Colour of rivers after rains	No change	Dirtier	Cleaner	None	Positive	Negative
	Health of coral reefs and aquatic ecosystems	No change	Less healthy	More healthy	None	Positive	Negative
	Alien plant species	No change	More	Fewer	None	Positive	Negative

Notes:

Perception of Mangroves

21. Do you think mangrove forests provide any benefits to Seychellois? (circle) Y / N

If so, what are they? _____

22. What benefits do you think mangroves have on the lagoon and reef? _____

23. Is there any link between mangroves and fish populations? (circle) Y / N

If so, what are they? _____

24. Do you think mangroves should be protected? (*circle*)

Y / N

If so, why? _____

25. Do you think mangroves should be replanted? (*circle*)

Y / N

If so, why? _____
